

MeTChE PROJECT INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

The Mediterranean Through Chinese Eyes

TRANSCULTURAL ENCOUNTERS AND REPRESENTATION IN CHINESE SOURCES

Book of abstracts

The Mediterranean Through Chinese Eyes: Transcultural Encounters and Representation in Chinese Sources

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The international conference *The Mediterranean Through Chinese Eyes: Transcultural Encounters and Representation in Chinese Sources* is the second conference of the MeTChE research project. This event aims to investigate how the Mediterranean has been perceived, represented, and reimagined in Chinese sources across time. Bringing together scholars from diverse disciplines, the conference will explore the construction of a transcultural perception of Mediterranean civilization(s) in Chinese geographical texts and travel diaries. Particular attention will be given to how representations of the sea and distant lands contributed to shaping the image of the “other” in Chinese thought.

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INTRODUCTION

Looking Back, Looking Forward: Tracing the Journey of the MeTChE Project

Renata Vinci (University of Palermo)

The *Mediterranean Through Chinese Eyes* (MeTChE) research project explores Chinese perceptions of the Mediterranean as a transcultural space from the Song to the Qing dynasties (960–1911). Officially launched in October 2023, and funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research with support from European Union funds (PRIN Projects, PNRR framework), MeTChE builds on years of previous research by its members and other scholars, with the aim of systematizing and re-elaborating the study of Sino-Mediterranean interactions from a transcultural perspective.

Combining Chinese Studies, Mediterranean Studies, Transcultural Studies, Studies on the Arab History of Geography, and Imagology, the project examines Chinese geographical treatises, travelogues, maps, and diplomatic writings to assess how the Mediterranean was described and conceptualized. It focuses on tracing the channels through which transcultural ideas about the Mediterranean reached China and identifying shared cultural traits across civilizations.

Coordinated by the University of Palermo, with contributions from three other Italian universities (Sapienza University of Rome, University of Florence, and University of Tuscia), MeTChE has achieved significant milestones, including:

- the first MeTChE conference, *The Mediterranean Through Chinese Eyes: An Intercultural Dialogue* (Viterbo, December 2024), which brought together scholars of Sino-Western contacts and Mediterranean Studies to share insights and methodologies;
- the edited volume *Navigating the Mediterranean Through the Chinese Lens: Transcultural Narratives of the Sea Among Lands* (Firenze University Press, 2024);
- the Italian-language podcast *Viaggio verso Occidente: Quando la Cina ha scoperto il Mediterraneo*, a 10-episode series exploring the lives and experiences of Chinese authors and travelers in the Mediterranean world.

Additionally, the MeTChE team is currently working on the digitization of the corpus of treatises, travelogues, maps, and diplomatic writings dealing with the Mediterranean, and on the development of a database to support future research and inquiries. This initiative aims to create a valuable resource to be shared with a broader scholarly community.

Beyond its scholarly outputs, MeTChE has fostered the creation of a growing network of researchers across Chinese Studies, Mediterranean Studies, and intercultural contact studies, strengthened through active participation in conferences and public events. By promoting the dissemination of its findings to schools and the wider public, MeTChE contributes to enhancing awareness of the historical interconnectedness between China and the Mediterranean, encouraging a more transcultural vision of past and present relations.

PANEL 1
First Glimpses of the Mediterranean:
Arab Knowledge and Early Chinese Accounts

The Role of Arab Sources in Shaping Chinese Geographical Knowledge from the IX to the XIV Century

Victoria Almonte (Tuscia University of Viterbo)

Daniele Sicari (University of Palermo)

This speech delves into the pivotal role played by geographers of the Arab-Islamic world in shaping Chinese geographical knowledge between the 9th and 14th centuries. The investigation highlights the contributions of figures such as Muḥammad Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī (781-847), Ibn Khurdādhbah (820-913), Šams al-Dīn al-Maqdisī (945-990), Yāqūt al-Ḥamawī (1178-1229), Šams al-Dīn al-Anṣārī (1256-1327), Ibn al-Wardī (1292-1349), and Ibn Baṭṭūṭa (1304-1368).

In conjunction with these Arab sources, the study examines coeval Chinese sources, such as the official geographical treatises (*zhi*) from the imperial dynasties, the *Jing Xing Ji* 經行紀 by Du Huan 杜環 (9th century) or the *Lingwai Daida* 嶺外代答 by Zhou Qufei 周去非 (1133-1181). They all provide a systematic presentation of Chinese geographical knowledge and reflect the Chinese perception of the Mediterranean as a fluid area of plurality and transculturality.

By cross-referencing Arab and Chinese sources, this research explores the convergence of geographical interests, particularly concerning the Mediterranean Sea as a crucial zone of interaction. It analyzes how these distinct cultural traditions perceived and documented the Mediterranean, revealing shared knowledge and mutual influences. This comparative analysis highlights the transculturality of geographical knowledge during this period and underscores the substantial impact of Arab-Islamic geographers on Chinese understandings of the world. Ultimately, this study demonstrates the interconnectedness of these cultures and emphasizes the importance of cross-cultural exchanges in shaping historical and geographical perspectives.

Searching for the Mediterranean in Wang Dayuan's Daoyi zhilüe: Toponyms and Debated Interpretations

Ileana Amadei (Sapienza University of Rome)

This contribution explores traces of the Mediterranean world in the *Daoyi zhilüe* 島夷誌略, a 14th-century work by Yuan dynasty traveller Wang Dayuan 汪大淵. Composed during a period of intensified East–West contact under Mongol rule, this work offers valuable geographical and ethnographic descriptions of numerous regions spanning the Indian Ocean and beyond. While European and Arab narratives of the Middle Ages often depict China and the East, this presentation asks whether Wang's work contains traces or indirect references to the Mediterranean world.

Focusing on contested entries, this contribution examines textual clues—such as geographical descriptions, local products, and cultural references—that have been variously interpreted as pointing to the Mediterranean world. Though the identification of some toponyms remains debated,

they reflect broader discussions about the extent of Chinese geographical knowledge and cultural encounters during the Yuan period.

Princely Power and Empire in Rabban Sauma's Account of the Western Mediterranean in the "History of Mar Yahballaha and Rabban Sauma"

Margaret Kim (National Tsinghua University)

In 1287, the Ilkhan Arghun, seeking an alliance with Latin Europe against Islamic states, dispatched Rabban Sauma, a Turkic monk of the Church of the East (popularly known as the Nestorian Church) from northern China, on a mission to the Latin West as his envoy. Sauma became the first known Chinese-born man to reach the Western Mediterranean as the Ilkhan's envoy. Even though Sauma's original account of his visit to the European Mediterranean in Persian is now lost, a shortened redacted translation of his account survives in the anonymous Syriac *History of Mar Yahballaha and Rabban Sauma*. Because Rabban Sauma's influence on the anonymous author in the composition of this historical work was significant, his account of Europeans and Mediterranean lands has to be understood within the *History* as a whole. My paper focuses on the representation of European rulers in the *History*. In particular, I analyze Rabban Sauma's consistently favorable portrayal of European rulers as benevolent princes within the framework of Sauma's connections to the Mongol elite. I examine the meaning of this flattering representation of European rulers with respect to the mighty power of the contemporary Mongol empire and Rabban Sauma's viewpoint as a Chinese-born Turkic monk. I suggest that the European Mediterranean and the Christian princes that Rabban Sauma met serve, in the *History*, as a series of exemplary lessons for the Mongol elite. While European princes are characterized as righteous Christian rulers, Sauma's portrayal of them in fact supports his own celebration of Mongol imperial dignity.

PANEL 2 Mapping the Mediterranean in Sino-Missionary Sources

Mediterranean World in Sino-Jesuit Geographical Sources

Paolo De Troia (Sapienza University of Rome)

This paper examines how the Mediterranean region was portrayed in Chinese-language geographical texts produced by Jesuit missionaries in the late Ming and early Qing dynasties. Focusing in particular on works such as Giulio Aleni's *Zhifang waiji* 職方外紀 and Matteo Ricci's *Kunyu wanguo quantu* 坤輿萬國全圖, the study explores how Jesuits translated and adapted European geographical knowledge for a Chinese audience. Through both textual descriptions and cartographic representations, these sources introduced Chinese readers to the historical and cultural significance of the Mediterranean world. The paper considers the strategies used by the Jesuits to convey unfamiliar places, including the use of neologisms and lexical adaptations. Countries such as Italy, or the so-called Judea, are given particular attention, not only for their geographical placement but also for their symbolic roles within the Jesuit effort to build intellectual and religious bridges between Europe and China. In doing so, the missionaries navigated complex cultural differences, blending European historical narratives with Chinese cultural frameworks. Ultimately, this research highlights the role of these texts in shaping a new, hybrid worldview and offers insight into the broader processes of early modern cross-cultural exchange and knowledge production.

19th-Century Geographic Writings in Chinese and Their Depictions of the Mediterranean Region: An Overview of Agencies and Approaches

Federica Casalin (Sapienza University of Rome)

In the 19th century, geography emerged as a scientific discipline in Europe and North America. Consequently, it witnessed a variety of disciplinary transitions, such as the development of new taxonomic criteria and the emergence of regional geography that transcended (unsteady) national boundaries. The "invention of the Mediterranean" (Deprest 2002) as a distinct geographic region happened first in Germany and then in France (Seirinidou 2023); the concept of a region centered on a "sea among lands" then reached North America and prompted regional studies on other possible "Mediterraneans" (Gillman 2022).

During the same century, China witnessed a flourishing activity of translation/adaptation of Western geographic sources, particularly after the first Opium War (1839-1842); this activity facilitated the transition from tradition to modernity in Chinese geographic thought (Zou 2007) and contributed to the designing of encyclopedic works on world geography published from the 1830s' to the 1850s', such as Lin Zexu's *Sizhouzhi* 四洲志 (*A Treatise on the Four Continents*), Xu Jiyu's *Yinghuan zhilue* 瀛寰志略 (*A Brief Account of the Maritime Circuit*), and Wei Yuan's *Haiguo tuzhi* 海國圖志 (*Illustrated Treatise on the Kingdoms Overseas*), followed by Wang Xiqi's *Xiaofanghu zhai yudi congchao* 小方壺齋與地叢鈔 (*A Collection of Geographic Writings of the Small Square Jug Hall*) in the 1890s.

This paper employs a macroanalytical approach to examine the representations of the territories associated with the Mediterranean region in a diverse array of 19th-century Chinese geographic sources. It highlights the contribution of various agents, such as Protestant missionaries and Chinese scholars, to the advancement of geographic knowledge regarding the “Sea among lands” (*Dizhonghai* 地中海) and the territories it encompasses. In doing so, it intends to contribute to assess the extent to which the Mediterranean may have been perceived and characterized as a distinct anthropogeographic region in China during the 19th century.

Did Religion Shape History? On William Muirhead’s (1822-1900) “Dili quanzhi 地理全志” and its Influence on Early Chinese Travelogues to Europe, with a Focus on the Representation of Religions Across the Mediterranean

Laura Lettere (Sapienza University of Rome)

William Muirhead (Mu Weilian 慕維廉, 1822–1900) was a Protestant missionary affiliated with the London Missionary Society and active in China since 1847. The list of his publications in Chinese, updated to the year 1867, includes 39 titles, most of which are hymns and doctrinal works. An important exception is the two-volume *Dili quanzhi* 地理全志 (Complete Treatise on Geography), published in Shanghai in the years 1853–1854.

While drawing upon earlier treatises such as Wei Yuan’s 魏源 (1794-1857) *Haiguo tuzhi* 海國圖志 (Illustrated Treatise on the Kingdoms Overseas), Xu Jiyu’s 徐繼畲 (1795-1873) *Yinghuan zhilüe* 瀛環志略 (1849), and the works of Karl Gützlaff 郭士立 (1803-1851) — notably the *Wanguo dili quanji* 萬國地理全集 (Complete Collection on World Geography) compiled between 1830-1838 —, Muirhead’s *Dili quanzhi* introduced novel elements. Among them was the emphasis on the use of traditional Chinese calendrical and dynastic references in narrating the histories of European nations, bridging Western historiography and Chinese chronological conventions.

This contribution will introduce possible research inquiries into the influence of the *Dili quanzhi* on the accounts of early Chinese travelers to Europe. A notable case is the translator Wang Tao 王韜 (1828–1897) and his diary *Manyou suilu* 漫遊隨錄 (Casual Records of my Wanderings) documenting his stay in Great Britain from 1867 to 1870. It is reported that Wang Tao and Muirhead crossed paths on several occasions during this period. These encounters offer valuable insight into the lives of early British sinologists and the intellectual exchanges between Chinese reformist thinkers and Protestant missionaries in the late Qing period.

Having established the relevance of Muirhead’s *Dili quanzhi* in shaping later Chinese odeporic literature, the study will further examine how geographical discourse in missionary and secular sources informed Chinese perceptions of global religions. Special attention will be given to the presentation—and, in the case of Calvinist Protestantism, the occasional censorship—of religions across the Mediterranean. Catholicism and Islam, in particular, will be analyzed as transcultural phenomena, with their influence on art, customs, and social institutions across the Mediterranean Sea.

PANEL 3

Routes and Reflections: Travels, Encounters and Representations of the Mediterranean in Early Modern and Modern Times

Beyond the Well: The Mediterranean Landscapes of Guo Liancheng

Miriam Castorina (University of Florence)

When Guo Liancheng 郭連城 (1839-1866) picked up his pen on 5 April 1859 to write the foreword to his account, he knew he was about to embark on an extraordinary adventure: a voyage from China to Italy. Others before him had sailed the oceans to travel this far, but their writings had remained in manuscript, and no one had ever seen them. His meticulously documented account of his voyage, *Xiyou bilüe* 西游筆略 (Brief Account of the Journey to the West, p. 1863), was one of the first overseas reports to be printed and was the first personal account of the Mediterranean, at a time when the Suez Canal was under construction and technological advances were making travel increasingly practical and faster. Through the goodwill and with the help of the writings of the Jesuits and Protestant missionaries, Guo Liancheng's Mediterranean landscapes offer an extraordinary insight into how a narrative of the Mediterranean found its way to China.

Travellers in the Late Qing Dynasty on the Political Landscape of the Mediterranean

Yu Yating (University of Florence)

Travellers' observation of Mediterranean Europe's political landscape during the late Qing and early Republic of China can be viewed as a microcosm of modern China's "opening its eyes to the world". This phenomenon also serves as a critical and implicit reflection on China's destiny, witnessing the clash of civilisations at the early stage of globalisation. This paper aims to analyse the diaries and notes of Chinese officials who journeyed to the Mediterranean area (including Italy, Greece, Egypt, and the Ottoman Empire) during the late Qing Dynasty and early Republican period, as included in the anthology *Zouxiang shijie congshu* 走向世界叢書 (From East to West) and *Zouxiang shijie congshu xubian* 走向世界叢書續編 (From East to West continued), edited by Zhong Shuhe 鍾叔河 (1931-). The following three points are utilised to explore the late Qing travellers' observations on the monarchies and political systems of these regions: 1) comparative and interdisciplinary research methods (utilising Antconc software), 2) intertextuality of text and history, and 3) a consideration of the Qing Dynasty from the perspective of travellers and literati, for reflections on the modern age. The paper examines the original text of *Zouxiang shijie congshu* and *Zouxiang shijie congshu xubian*, analysing the travellers' observations and evaluations of the monarchical systems of the Mediterranean, as well as their reflections on the politics and culture of China. The text is further explored to examine how the traveller-officials and literati balanced tradition with modernity and the local with the foreign during the late Qing and early Republican period.

Quotation as a Deliberate Act in Zhang Deyi's Acquaintance of the Mediterranean

Antonio Leggieri (University of Palermo)

Zhang Deyi's 張德彝 (1847-1919) travelogues have been read as a reliable "Chinese lens" through which a sensitive student-interpreter-diplomat observed the world outside China. Scholars have repeatedly emphasised his precision, attention to detail, and objectiveness. However, as his writing matured, he began interspersing his travelogues with more or less known quotations from the Chinese classics, such as the *Hanshi Waizhuan* 韓詩外傳 (Outer commentary by Master Han), or by such lesser-known men of letters as Sun Ti 孫逖 or Zhen Shanmin 真山民, together with more evident quotations from the classics (for example, the *Shiji* 史記) and master texts (in order of frequency, Mengzi 孟子, Zhuangzi 莊子, and Liezi 列子).

This paper aims at identifying the places and occasions which, in Zhang's mind, called for quotations from the classics. In turn, these quotations added gravitas to his diaries, established a connection with the past, and informed Zhang's perception of the Mediterranean. It is a widely accepted truism that quotation is an attempt at capturing an actuality which exists in both the quoted text and in the new one; moreover, explicit quotations, such as the ones that Zhang uses, are now seen as the quoting voice's "active intervention" (Bal, 1999) upon its own tradition, and as Canettieri (2012) stated, the practice of quotation is what emerges from our innate tendency to combine disparate elements when we create. It is then important to pin down the sources with which Zhang "recreated" the Mediterranean in his writings.

Italian Renaissance Art and China's New Culture Movement

Feng Lisi (Nankai University)

The Renaissance represents a monumental historical era, particularly marked by the flourishing of Italian Renaissance achievements across numerous fields. Florence emerged as the epicenter of the Renaissance, recognized as the birthplace and primary area of humanist thought in Europe. The Renaissance broke the cultural constraints of medieval religious ideology, similar to how the May Fourth Movement dismantled the cultural restrictions imposed by the feudal monarchical system in China.

Many modern Chinese intellectuals sought to integrate Chinese tradition with Western modernity, leading to extensive discussions on Renaissance art. Xue Fucheng 薛福成 praised Rome for gathering the finest Master of Art and lauded the realistic technique of imitating nature. Kang Youwei 康有為 compared Raphael with renowned figures from ancient China, stating that his paintings resembled "the calligraphy of Wang Xizhi 王羲之, the poetry of Li Bai 李白, and the prose of Su Shi 蘇軾". Kang viewed realistic painting as a significant existing tradition in Chinese art, thereby situating his ideal of "integrating Chinese and Western art to create a new era" within the framework of his philosophy of "renewal through a return to the classics". Chen Duxiu 陳獨秀's theory of artistic revolution carried a strong emphasis on cultural holism, underscoring the need for a comprehensive transformation in

art and culture. Liang Qichao 梁啟超 highlighted the relationship between art and science, urging artists to study science and observe nature, much like Leonardo da Vinci. Figures such as Cai Yuanpei 蔡元培 and Lu Xun 魯迅 emphasized realism and social engagement in the arts. Their proposals for artistic reform, although seemingly similar on the surface, have fundamentally different value systems and logical structures underlying them.

PANEL 4
Maritime Imaginaries and Global Horizons

Dietary Practices and Provisioning at Sea: Comparative Insights from Mediterranean, Spanish Pacific and Chinese Maritime Traditions (16-18th century)

Mathieu Torck (Ghent University/KU Leuven)

The advent of the Age of Sail brought along a wide range of challenges for seafaring crews, not in the least where health and hygiene during ever longer transoceanic crossings was concerned. Sailors' daily livelihood which initially constituted a continuation of traditional mainland diets underwent major changes. In the past few decades, historical epidemiology and anthropology, as well as bioarchaeology have increasingly studied dietary patterns at sea, their related pathologies and disastrous outcomes from different angles, covering European as well as extra-European contexts (Torck 2009; Badura *et. al.* 2013; Lamb 2020). The vitamin C deficiency scurvy, a direct result of insufficient nutritional intake consumed aboard early modern seagoing ships during long-haul expeditions of a mercantile or military character, serves as a central case. In the spirit of Braudel's investigation of the interactions between Mediterranean maritime activities with hinterland agricultural production and trade centers, this paper aims to shed light on variations in early modern maritime food supply through the application of a gradual historical-spatial approach. The first step will be an attempt to trace and review the origins of seafaring crews' food supply in the more localized geographical environments of the Iberian/Mediterranean seafaring world (Mott 2018). This will enable an analysis of the correlation between local shipboard dietary practices and their continuation or adaptation to much more extensive transoceanic expeditions in the Spanish Pacific space (Ruiz Garcia 2022). Finally, shipboard diets will be discussed in a comparative, cross-cultural perspective which also involves Chinese and intra-Asian seafaring traditions with the goal to understand different modes of adaptation in shipboard food supply, including such key notions as preservation and tropicalization. Eventually, this paper probes into deeper-lying causes that explain why the composition of the diet and the socio-economically determined deviations from mainland foodways caused high mortality rates among early modern seafaring crews.

Changing Perceptions of the Northern Terra Incognita Across Eurasia from Antiquity to the Middle Ages

Alexander Jost (LMU München)

Long before the ends of the Eurasian continent entered an age of persistent direct exchange and interaction, topoi and narratives addressing the unknown lands of the far north show stunning similarities. Although a number of natural and cultural phenomena encountered by people travelling north from temperate latitudes can be observed similarly in China, Central Asia, or Europe, the resemblances go much further — raising the question to what extent they were the result of communication.

This presentation demonstrates different instances and discusses possible patterns of exchange in the field of imagined geographies of the far North using as examples the term of Ultima Thule, the phenomenon of polar utopiae or legends like the ones of the horse-legged people or the pygmies and the cranes. Beside potential exchanges of information across the Eurasian landmass along the earliest avenues of exchange and communication, through the analysis of these narratives also a chronology of changes in the perception of the Eurasian North can become apparent leading from purely speculative images serving mainly the purpose of cosmological explanation through fantastic, exoticizing and exaggerated descriptions from hearsay down to much more realistic reports from travellers referring to their own eyewitness observations - a genre to be especially encountered during the Mongol period.

